

HVI-SMM : Spatially-Adaptive Correction for Low-Light Image Enhancement

Injea Lee, Sungho Kang, Juneho Yi

Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Sungkyunkwan University,
Suwon 16419, Republic of Korea.
{injea1291, sungho369, jhyi}@skku.edu

Abstract Low-Light Image Enhancement aims to restore images captured under poor illumination conditions. Previous methods that apply uniform correction across the entire image fail to adjust local illumination variations, leading to noise amplification in dark regions and oversaturation in bright regions. To address these limitations, we propose Spatial Modulation Module (SMM) based on the Horizontal/Vertical-Intensity (HVI) color space. SMM captures contextual information and dynamically generates saturation and brightness correction maps in a pixel-wise manner. We introduce Intensity Mean Loss designed to adaptively balance brightness alignment and detail restoration based on distribution divergence. This loss guides the network to focus on structural detail restoration. We also employ Intermediate Supervision Loss to resolve the scale ambiguity problem in SMM, ensuring training stability. Experimental results on diverse datasets demonstrated that HVI-SMM achieved superior performance improvements, validating the effectiveness of pixel-wise optimization for sophisticated local restoration. The code is publicly available ¹.

Key Words Low-Light Image Enhancement, HVI Color Space, Spatial Modulation Module, Intensity Mean Loss, Intermediate Supervision Loss

1 Introduction

Low-Light Image Enhancement (LLIE) is a critical problem in restoring images captured under poor illumination conditions, yet it faces a fundamental challenge: the ambiguity in defining the sufficient illumination condition. That is, the Ground Truth (GT) images for LLIE can vary significantly in brightness and color appearance depending on the photographer’s exposure settings and subjective aesthetic preferences. Even when a model perfectly recovers structural details, the global brightness or saturation of the restored result may not align with user intentions or the statistical distribution of the GT.

Recent works [1, 3, 4, 5, 12, 14, 17] have adopted global scalar parameters that allow users to adjust brightness during inference. These works ignore local image characteristics, leading to negative effects such as noise amplification in dark regions and saturation clipping in bright regions. To address this limitation, we propose a novel approach dubbed HVI-SMM. The Spatial Modulation Module (SMM) dynamically generates saturation and brightness correction maps optimized for each pixel based

1. <https://github.com/int11/HVI-SMM>

Figure 1. Comparison of limitations of global correction methods and the proposed method. (a) Original low-light image, (b) Global correction result: noise and color distortion due to uniform amplification of brightness and saturation, (c) Proposed spatially-adaptive correction result: sharp restoration through pixel-wise optimization, (d) Ground truth image.

on the Horizontal/Vertical-Intensity (HVI) [14] color space. The proposed method effectively predicts pixel-wise correction intensities instead of uniform global adjustments. We also introduce an intermediate supervision loss to resolve the scale ambiguity during training process. The proposed approach enables spatially-adaptive restoration by suppressing corrections in noisy regions while emphasizing vivid colors.

Previous works [2, 7, 9] suggest that human vision is primarily sensitive to noise artifacts and color fidelity under sufficient illumination conditions. In pixel-wise loss functions, brightness residuals dominate the loss value, causing networks to prioritize simple brightness matching over the more perceptually important tasks of noise removal and color restoration. Thus, we introduce an intensity mean loss. This loss prevents brightness residuals from dominating the loss function and guides the network to focus on structural detail restoration and color fidelity.

As illustrated in Figure 1, our approach effectively suppresses noise amplification and saturation clipping through spatially-adaptive correction. Experiments on diverse datasets confirm the effectiveness of our approach.

2 Color space

In low-light conditions, RGB color space induces color distortion due to the linear dependence between brightness and color. HSV color space suffers red discontinuity noise in the hue channel, h , and amplifies artifacts known as black plane noise in the saturation channel, s . To overcome these limitations, we adopt the HVI color space [14] that transforms the one-dimensional h into a two-dimensional, $(\mathcal{H}, \mathcal{V})$, as in (1). Furthermore, it employs an intensity-dependent collapse function to suppress noise in dark regions.

$$\mathcal{H} = C_k \odot s \odot \cos\left(\frac{\pi h}{3}\right), \quad \mathcal{V} = C_k \odot s \odot \sin\left(\frac{\pi h}{3}\right) \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. The architecture of HVI-SMM. The input image is converted to the HVI color space and passes through a dual-branch UNet. Subsequently, the output image is precisely corrected pixel-wise through spatially-adaptive correction maps generated by SMM.

Here, $C_k(v) = \sqrt[k]{\sin(\frac{\pi v}{2}) + \epsilon}$. $C_k(v)$ is the intensity-dependent collapse function that maps low-light pixels to zero. This prevents noise artifacts in s from degrading the output. To clarify, \odot denotes the Hadamard product.

3 Proposed method

3.1 HVI-SMM architecture

As shown in Figure 2, the overall architecture of HVI-SMM is based on a dual-branch UNet. The input image is converted to the HVI color space, where color restoration ($\mathcal{H}\mathcal{V}$ branch) and brightness enhancement (\mathcal{I} branch) are performed separately, with mutual information complemented through Lighten Cross-Attention [14]. The SMM predicts spatial correction maps based on intermediate feature maps; $\hat{\alpha}_s$ for saturation and $\hat{\alpha}_i$ for brightness. The output image is computed as follows:

$$\hat{h} = \frac{3}{\pi} \arctan\left(\frac{\hat{\mathcal{V}}}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}}\right) \bmod 6, \quad \hat{s} = \hat{\alpha}_s \odot \frac{\sqrt{\hat{\mathcal{H}}^2 + \hat{\mathcal{V}}^2}}{C_k + \epsilon}, \quad \hat{v} = \hat{\mathcal{I}} \odot \hat{\alpha}_i \quad (2)$$

Through this process, the network achieves spatially-adaptive restoration by suppressing corrections in noisy regions and emphasizing areas requiring sharpness.

3.2 Loss function

We employ the following \mathcal{L}_{IntSup} as the loss function for training.

$$\mathcal{L}_{IntSup} = \mathcal{L}_{IntMean}(I_{out}, I_{GT}) + \lambda_{IntSup} \cdot \mathcal{L}_{IntMean}(I_{base}, I_{GT}) \quad (3)$$

Because we apply \mathcal{L}_{IntSup} to the intermediate output, I_{base} , to resolve the scale ambiguity problem, this loss is dubbed **Intermediate Supervision Loss**. Given

the decomposition $I_{out} = I_{base} \odot \text{SMM}$, without explicit constraints, the solution is not uniquely determined. This poses a risk of converging to a degenerate solution where I_{base} fails to faithfully restore image structure and illumination, while the SMM takes on the full burden of brightness amplification. To prevent this, we impose a loss between I_{base} and GT to force the base network to restore basic illumination and structure. This ensures training stability. This intermediate supervision loss guides the SMM to focus on local brightness and saturation correction rather than merely serving as a simple intensity scaling factor.

Intensity Mean Loss, $\mathcal{L}_{IntMean}(\cdot, \cdot)$. Conventional pixel-wise loss functions tend to overemphasize weights on reducing brightness residuals rather than on noise removal or color restoration when a brightness mismatch occurs between the GT and predicted images [7]. To address this, we introduce $\mathcal{L}_{IntMean}$ based on the distribution difference of the \mathcal{I} in the HVI color space. Let P and Q be the probability distributions of the \mathcal{I} in the image, \mathcal{I}_I and \mathcal{I} in the GT, \mathcal{I}_{IGT} . We measure the difference between the distributions using Jensen-Shannon Divergence (JSD) to define the weight, formulated as $W = \text{clamp}(\text{JSD}(P||Q), 0, 1)$, and apply it to the loss function as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{IntMean}(I, I_{GT}) = W \cdot \mathcal{L}_{basic}(I, I_{GT}) + (1 - W) \cdot \mathcal{L}_{basic}\left(\frac{\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{I}_{IGT}]}{\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{I}_I]}I, I_{GT}\right) \quad (4)$$

Here, $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ denotes the spatial averaging operator. Thus, $\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{I}_I]$ and $\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{I}_{IGT}]$ correspond to the global mean intensity values calculated over the spatial dimensions of the predicted map and the GT map $\in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times H \times W}$, respectively. When the distribution difference is large ($W \approx 1$), this loss function drives the network to concentrate on global brightness alignment. As the distributions become similar ($W \approx 0$), the loss shifts towards precise tuning such as noise suppression.

Basic Loss, $\mathcal{L}_{basic}(\cdot, \cdot)$. We employ \mathcal{L}_{basic} as a weighted combination of L_1 , SSIM [11], Edge [8], and Perceptual [6] losses in both HVI and RGB color spaces to ensure color restoration and structural similarity.

$$\mathcal{L}_{basic}(\hat{I}, I) = \lambda_1 \cdot L_1(\hat{I}, I) + \lambda_d \cdot L_{SSIM}(\hat{I}, I) + \lambda_e \cdot L_{Edge}(\hat{I}, I) + \lambda_p \cdot L_{Perceptual}(\hat{I}, I) \quad (5)$$

4 Experiments

We trained our model on the LOLv1 [12], LOLv2-Real [16], and LOLv2-Synthetic [16] datasets with a single NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080Ti GPU, Adam optimizer, and Cosine Annealing scheduler. LOLv1 and LOLv2-Real were cropped to 400×400 and trained for 1,500 epochs, while LOLv2-Synthetic was trained at its original resolution for 500 epochs.

Table 1. Quantitative performance comparison on each dataset. FLOPs are measured on a single 256×256 image.

Methods	Complexity		LOLv1 [12]			LOLv2-Real [16]			LOLv2-Synthetic [16]		
	Params/M	FLOPs/G	PSNR \uparrow	SSIM \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow	PSNR \uparrow	SSIM \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow	PSNR \uparrow	SSIM \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow
RetinexNet [12]	0.840	584.470	16.770	0.560	-	16.097	0.401	0.543	17.137	0.762	0.255
SNR-Aware [13]	4.010	26.350	23.005	0.824	0.164	21.103	0.839	0.169	24.173	0.924	0.064
RetinexFormer [3]	1.530	15.850	23.830	0.832	0.141	21.272	0.841	0.163	25.281	0.928	0.064
LLFormer [10]	24.550	22.520	23.007	0.805	0.183	21.308	0.803	0.248	24.195	0.918	0.070
CIDNet [14]	1.980	7.910	23.809	0.857	0.086	24.111	0.871	0.108	25.130	0.939	0.045
HVI-CIDNet+ [15]	300.880	23.540	-	-	-	24.308	0.873	0.107	25.982	0.943	0.040
HVI-SMM(Ours)	2.000	9.840	24.357	0.861	0.072	24.664	0.872	0.117	26.084	0.941	0.042

Figure 3. Visualization of spatial correction maps. In achromatic regions (white binder), $\hat{\alpha}_s$ is predicted to be low to suppress color noise, while $\hat{\alpha}_i$ appears high to restore visibility. In chromatic regions (wooden frame), both $\hat{\alpha}_s$ and $\hat{\alpha}_i$ show high values to revive the desaturated colors. In complex multi-colored regions (bookshelf), $\hat{\alpha}_s$ is kept low to prevent color bleeding, while $\hat{\alpha}_i$ is elevated to ensure readability.

As shown in Table 1, we compared our method with Transformer- and diffusion-based models [3, 10, 12, 13] to validate its effectiveness. The proposed method demonstrates competitive performance in terms of PSNR, SSIM, and LPIPS. In particular, our method clearly outperforms CIDNet [14]. Moreover, our method achieves performance comparable to CIDNet+ [15] with significantly lower complexity, which demonstrates superior efficiency. This confirms the effectiveness of the proposed approach. Figure 3 shows that the predicted correction maps reveal distinct spatial distributions. This demonstrates that replacing global scalars with pixel-wise maps enables content-aware selective correction and noise suppression.

5 Conclusion

We proposed HVI-SMM, a novel low-light enhancement model that generates pixel-wise correction maps through the Spatial Modulation Module and ensures training stability with Intermediate Supervision Loss, while focusing on structural restoration via Intensity Mean Loss. Experimental results confirmed consistent performance improvements and content-aware adaptive restoration through correction map analysis.

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